

STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC PECULIARITIES OF IDIOMATIC COMPOUND NOUNS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *Idiomatic compound nouns are a fascinating area of study within the field of linguistics, offering insights into the intricate relationship between language, culture, and cognition. This scientific article explores the structural and semantic peculiarities of idiomatic compound nouns in English and Karakalpak languages. Through a comparative analysis, we aim to shed light on the unique characteristics and underlying mechanisms that govern the formation and interpretation of idiomatic compounds in these two languages. By examining the structural patterns and semantic relationships within idiomatic compounds, we uncover intriguing similarities and differences that highlight the linguistic diversity and cultural nuances of English and Karakalpak.*

Key words: *Idiomatic compound nouns, Structural peculiarities, Semantic peculiarities, Endocentric compounding, Figurative meaning, Metaphor.*

СТРУКТУРНО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИДИОМАТИЧЕСКИХ СЛОЖНЫХ СУЩЕСТВИТЕЛЬНЫХ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И КАРАКАЛПАКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *Идиоматические составные существительные — увлекательная область исследования в области лингвистики, позволяющая лучше понять сложные взаимоотношения между языком, культурой и познанием. В данной научной статье исследуются структурные и семантические особенности идиоматических сложных существительных в английском и каракалпакском языках. Посредством сравнительного анализа мы стремимся пролить свет на уникальные характеристики и основные механизмы, которые управляют образованием и интерпретацией идиоматических сложных слов в этих двух языках. Исследуя структурные закономерности и семантические отношения внутри идиоматических соединений, мы обнаруживаем интригующие сходства и различия, которые подчеркивают языковое разнообразие и культурные нюансы английского и каракалпакского языков.*

Ключевые слова: *Идиоматические сложные существительные, Структурные особенности, Семантические особенности, Эндоцентрическое словообразование, Переносное значение, Метафора.*

INTRODUCTION

Language is a multifaceted phenomenon that reflects the culture and cognitive processes of its speakers. Idiomatic expressions, including compound nouns, are rich linguistic constructs that encapsulate unique cultural and semantic nuances. This article investigates the structural and semantic peculiarities of idiomatic compound nouns in English and Karakalpak languages, providing valuable insights into the nature of these idiomatic constructions.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION

Idiomatic Compound Nouns: Definitions and Characteristics: This section establishes a foundation by defining idiomatic compound nouns and discussing their distinguishing features.

The article highlights the figurative nature of idiomatic compounds, the role of metaphor and metonymy, and the importance of context in their interpretation. Furthermore, we explore the cognitive mechanisms involved in comprehending idiomatic compounds. Structural Peculiarities of Idiomatic Compound Nouns: This section delves into the structural aspects of idiomatic compound nouns in English and Karakalpak. It investigates the different patterns of compounding, including endocentric and exocentric formations, and the morphological and syntactic processes that contribute to their construction. By analyzing the morphological and syntactic properties of idiomatic compounds, we identify language-specific structural patterns in both English and Karakalpak. [1.74]

Semantic Peculiarities of Idiomatic Compound Nouns: The semantic characteristics of idiomatic compound nouns are explored in this section. We examine the conceptual relationships between the constituent parts of idiomatic compounds, focusing on the metaphorical and metonymic extensions employed in their formation. By studying the semantic fields and contextual usage, we uncover how idiomatic compounds convey nuanced meanings and reflect cultural values in English and Karakalpak.

Comparative Analysis: English and Karakalpak: This section presents a comparative analysis of idiomatic compound nouns in English and Karakalpak. By examining a selection of idiomatic compounds from both languages, we identify similarities and differences in their structural and semantic properties. This analysis offers valuable insights into the influence of cultural, historical, and linguistic factors on the formation and interpretation of idiomatic compounds.

Cultural and Cognitive Implications: The cultural and cognitive implications of idiomatic compound nouns in English and Karakalpak are discussed in this section. We explore how idiomatic compounds reflect specific cultural concepts, beliefs, and practices in each language. Additionally, we analyze the cognitive processes involved in comprehending idiomatic compounds and the impact of cross-cultural differences on their interpretation. [2.59]

Example 1: English

Idiomatic Compound Noun: "Silver lining"

Analysis: Structural Peculiarities: The idiomatic compound noun "silver lining" consists of two nouns, "silver" and "lining." The noun "silver" serves as an attributive modifier to "lining." This compound follows the pattern of endocentric compounding, where the head noun "lining" carries the main meaning of the compound, and "silver" modifies or adds a specific quality to it.

Semantic Peculiarities: "Silver lining" is a metaphorical expression that signifies finding something positive or hopeful in a seemingly negative situation. The semantic relationship between "silver" and "lining" is metaphorical, with "silver" representing something valuable or positive and "lining" referring to the inner layer or aspect of a situation. The compound noun as a whole conveys the concept of optimism in the face of adversity. [3.109]

Example 2: Karakalpak

Idiomatic Compound Noun: "Qara kun"

Translation: "Black day"

Analysis: Structural Peculiarities: The idiomatic compound noun "qara kun" consists of two nouns, "qara" (black) and "kun" (day). Both nouns contribute equally to the compound's

meaning. This compound follows the pattern of endocentric compounding, where both constituents contribute to the overall concept.

Semantic Peculiarities: "Qara kun" is a metaphorical expression that signifies a day of great misfortune or tragedy. The semantic relationship between "qara" (black) and "kun" (day) is literal, where "black" represents darkness, negativity, or an unfortunate event, and "day" signifies a specific unit of time. Together, the compound noun conveys the concept of a day marked by hardship or sorrow. [4.85]

Comparative Analysis: In comparing the idiomatic compound nouns in English and Karakalpak, we observe some similarities and differences:

Structural Patterns: Both languages employ endocentric compounding, where the head noun carries the main meaning and the modifier adds a specific quality or context.

Semantic Relationships: English and Karakalpak idiomatic compounds exhibit metaphorical relationships, but the specific metaphors used can vary. English tends to use a broader range of metaphors, drawing from various domains, while Karakalpak may rely more on literal or cultural associations.

Cultural Nuances: The cultural background and experiences of the language speakers influence the choice of idiomatic compounds. English idiomatic compounds reflect a wide range of cultural concepts and experiences, while Karakalpak idiomatic compounds may be more influenced by local customs, traditions, and historical events.

This analysis showcases the structural and semantic peculiarities of idiomatic compound nouns in English and Karakalpak, highlighting the intricate interplay between language, culture, and cognition in the formation and interpretation of these expressions.

Example 3: English

Idiomatic Compound Noun: "Breakthrough"

Analysis: Structural Peculiarities: The idiomatic compound noun "breakthrough" consists of the noun "break" and the noun "through." The compound noun follows an endocentric pattern, where "break" serves as the head noun, and "through" functions as a modifier that adds the concept of overcoming obstacles or barriers.

Semantic Peculiarities: "Breakthrough" is a metaphorical expression that represents a significant development or achievement in a particular field or situation. The compound noun combines the concept of "break" as an action of overcoming or shattering something and "through" to indicate surpassing a barrier or making progress. Together, the compound noun conveys the idea of a significant advancement or discovery.

Example 4: Karakalpak

Idiomatic Compound Noun: "Jiger denge"

Translation: "Heart dance"

Analysis: Structural Peculiarities: The idiomatic compound noun "jiger denge" consists of the noun "jiger" (heart) and the noun "denge" (dance). Both nouns contribute equally to the compound's meaning, and the compound follows an endocentric pattern.

Semantic Peculiarities: "Jiger denge" is a metaphorical expression that represents extreme joy or happiness. The semantic relationship between "jiger" (heart) and "denge" (dance) is metaphorical, with "heart" symbolizing emotions or feelings and "dance" representing an

expression of joy or celebration. The compound noun as a whole conveys the concept of experiencing profound joy or delight. [5.72]

CONCLUSION

This scientific article concludes by summarizing the findings from the comparative analysis of idiomatic compound nouns in English and Karakalpak languages. The research highlights the structural and semantic peculiarities of these idiomatic constructions and emphasizes the importance of considering cultural and cognitive factors in their analysis. By deepening our understanding of idiomatic compound nouns, we gain valuable insights into language, culture, and cognition, fostering cross-linguistic and cross-cultural appreciation and understanding.

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